

Water quality monitoring using soft computing techniques in Udupi Region, Karnataka, India

Krishnamurthy Nayak¹, Sumukha K. Nayak², Supreetha Balavalikar Shivaram¹

¹Manipal Institute of Technology (MIT), Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Karnataka, India

²Birla Institute of Technology and Science (BITS), Rajasthan, India

Article Info

Article history:

Received Mar 25, 2024

Revised Jun 3, 2025

Accepted Sep 10, 2025

Keywords:

Decision tree algorithm

K-nearest neighbour algorithm

Mean squared error

National Rural Drinking Water

Programme

Water quality index

ABSTRACT

A monitoring of water quality index parameters using soft computing technology is the current research focus as the main challenge of which is to design a soft computing algorithm with the highest accuracy and less computation time. For the secondary dataset obtained by the government database, this research proposes a water quality prediction and classification method based on decision tree algorithm. The comparative analysis is made for the different highest accuracy algorithms like decision tree algorithm with support vector machine (SVM), k-nearest neighbour (KNN) classifier, linear discriminant analysis, Naïve Bayes classifier and logistic regression. Decision tree algorithm had the highest accuracy compared to other algorithms. The KNN algorithm used as clustering algorithm to plot the two classes good and bad. The trend analysis of the water quality is performed with various water quality parameters like pH, fluoride and total dissolved solids (TDS) test results are plotted and observed for the variations of the values with respect to increase in time. The performance is measured with statistical indices and the prediction accuracy of 0.99 and mean squared error of 0.05. The results prove that the KNN algorithm found to be better for clustering purposes.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Supreetha Balavalikar Shivaram

Manipal Institute of Technology (MIT), Manipal Academy of Higher Education

Tiger Circle Road, Madhav Nagar, Manipal, Udupi, Karnataka 576104, India

Email: supreetha.bs@manipal.edu

1. INTRODUCTION

The availability of pure and sufficient drinking water is the primary need of every human being. In this research work the southern part of India, Karnataka state is considered as study area. In Karnataka, with an increase in population, the quality of consumable water is degrading every day. Along with this, the consumption rate is increasing due to agricultural, industrial needs and other requirements [1], [2]. Scientists test the water quality by traditional water quality monitoring methods involving water sample collection, testing and finally investigation, which is done manually [3], [4]. This traditional approach is not fully reliable, and cost incurred is more and the requirement for manpower is a recurring process. Nowadays soft computing is a trending technology to predict water quality and various studies are carried out in predicting the concentration of various water parameters which helps in timely improving the water quality [5], [6]. Machine learning, when integrated with hardware systems consisting of sensors (such as pH, turbidity, temperature) and combined with the internet of things (IoT), can be used to design a real-time system to monitor the water quality of tanks installed in houses, hospitals, colleges, ponds, rivers [7], [8]. Water is the lifeline of all the living beings in this direction monitoring the water quality of water tanks installed in

houses/hospitals/colleges, ponds, rivers are very important [9], [10]. Here in this research work we are not focusing on the hardware implementation but rather only on the machine learning part of implementation.

Due to rapid increase in pollution, population and global warming the amount of clean drinking water is reducing every day [11], [12]. Therefore, there is a need for better methodologies for real-time water quality monitoring [13]. The central pollution control board (CPCB), in collaboration with the Karnataka State pollution control board (KSPCB), is implementing the national water monitoring program (NWMP) across 63 monitoring stations in the state [14], [15].

Chungyalpa [16] and Ravikumar *et al.* [17] investigated the assessment of water quality index (WQI) in the surface water of tank and lake water from Bangalore, Karnataka. They considered three sampling locations with a study period of 3 months during pre-monsoon season. They investigated a total of 14 parameters for physiochemical parameters. The study proves that the sodium adsorption ratio (SAR) values indicate that both the water bodies belong to the excellent class and are suitable for irrigation. There is a lot of research in surface water but limited research in groundwater quality. Giao *et al.* [18] discussed groundwater quality in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam using multivariate statistical method. They investigated a total of 8 water quality parameters from 64 sampling points. The results prove mixed results on groundwater quality and infer that the quality of groundwater depends on geological locations. Madrid and Zayas [19] investigated the issues related to monitoring practices on sampling in present scenarios. This work summarizes the points that need to be considered before sampling for chemical monitoring. Ahmed *et al.* [20] discuss issues and state-of-the-art technologies to address water quality. This work focusses on the advantages of modern technologies to monitor and assess water quality. They inferred that the latest technologies are an effective alternative to expensive laborious manual analysis. However, the traditional method of water quality monitoring is not feasible as the results are not so accurate and it is a time-consuming process to determine the water quality [21], [22]. Nayak *et al.* [23] explored the use of an electronic nose system integrated with an embedded peripheral interface controller (PIC) microcontroller to detect and quantify microbial contaminants. They analyzed assessment of water quality by detecting microbial water quality using experimental setup as well as embedded systems. The eNose system was found to be effective in detecting and accurately qualifying the microbial contaminants, specifically coliform group of bacteria.

Nowadays researchers are carrying out new inventions for determining water quality. In the engineering field much research is going on in the soft computing field. Due to machine learning engineers can design devices which communicate among themselves and accordingly analyse the data intelligently to produce the water quality. This paper mainly focuses on the best suitable method for computing the water quality of the water bodies available for drinking purposes. The proposed method deals with soft computing techniques applied to various water parameters to check for drinking water consumption purposes like pH, turbidity, temperature, and dissolved oxygen.

2. METHOD

2.1. Study area

Situated along the Arabian Sea coastline in Karnataka, Udupi district forms part of the western margin of peninsular India and is topographically delineated from the interior by the prominent Western Ghats [24]. The district's river systems discharge into the Arabian Sea and are subject to tidal influence over considerable distances inland [25], [26]. Contemporary water management practices, notably sprinkler irrigation, are witnessing increased adoption in this region. The geographical location of Udupi district is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Location map coastal area of Karnataka, Udupi

The original WQI dataset was obtained from National Rural Drinking Water Programme (NRDWP) Udupi District Karnataka which conducts regular monitoring of the quality of the rivers in Udupi, Karkala, Kondapur, Bhatkal taluks regularly. This dataset comprised of 5000 data points which is derived from measurements of 14 water quality parameters (fluoride, calcium, iron, total dissolved solids (TDS), nitrate, chloride, TH, pH, magnesium, sodium, potassium, sulphate, alkalinity, and turbidity). For this study, historical data from 2015-2017 were collected. The data were classified into two categories: class 0 (unfit for drinking) and class 1 (fit for drinking). Table 1 presents the water quality index of drinking water in India.

Table 1. Comparison of groundwater quality with drinking water standards, Indian and WHO [20]

Parameters	Indian standard	Percent compliance	WHO standard	Percent compliance
pH	6.5-8.5	98.5	7-8	91
TDS	500	70	1000	96.5
Total hardness as CaCO_3 , mg/l	300	70	100	0.5
Chloride mg/l	250	97	250	97
Sulphate mg/l	200	100	250	100
Nitrate mg/l	45	51.5	50	56.5
Fluoride mg/l	1	30	1	30
Calcium mg/l	75	96	75	96
Magnesium mg/l	30	26	30	26
Iron mg/l	0.3	0.5	0.1	0.5
Manganese	0.1	17	0.05	17

2.2. Materials and method

The machine learning algorithms support vector machines (SVM), classification decision tree, linear discriminant analysis, logistic regression, Naïve Bayes, (used for variable importance tasks, regression and classification), K-nearest neighbours (KNN) and k-means clustering (used for unsupervised-classification) are employed to develop the WQI prediction and classification model. In this study, we evaluated the performance of six algorithms using a water quality dataset comprising 5,000 samples. The flowchart of the proposed model is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Flowchart of the proposed model

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The model performance was evaluated using statistical indices and prediction accuracy. Table 2 presents the overall mean and standard deviation with type accuracy scores. Figure 3 depicts the box-whisker plot of algorithm accuracy, highlighting the variance and mean values used to determine the best-fit model for the study. Figures 4 and 5, illustrates the distribution of 5,000 water samples through a box-whisker plot and histogram respectively, while Figure 6 shows the covariance plot of all 14 input water quality parameters along with the corresponding class type.

Table 2. Table of overall mean and standard deviation with scoring of type accuracy

Algorithm	Mean (accuracy)	Standard deviation (accuracy)
Logistic regression	0.994228	0.002884
Linear discriminant analysis (LDA)	0.991582	0.001319
KNN	0.968257	0.007843
Decision tree	0.995189	0.992427
Naïve Bayes	0.968505	0.031018
SVM	0.97908	0.010627

Figure 3. Algorithmic accuracy comparison

Figure 4. Dataset distribution plot: Box and Whisker plot

Figure 5. Data distribution plot: histogram plot

Figure 6. Covariance plot of data distribution

Among all the algorithms evaluated, the decision tree achieved the highest accuracy and was therefore selected for further analysis. The model attained a mean square error (MSE) of 0.05 and an accuracy of 0.9934895. The detailed classification report of the decision tree algorithm is presented in Table 3, while Figure 7 illustrates the trend analysis of the 14 water quality parameters from 2015 to 2018.

Table 3. Classification report of decision tree algorithm

Classification report	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Support
Class 0	0.86	0.8	0.83	15
Class 1	1	1	1	753
Micro Average	0.99	0.99	0.99	768
Macro average	0.93	0.9	0.91	768
Weighted average	0.99	0.99	0.99	768

Figure 7. Trend analysis of water quality parameters

Figures 8 and 9 show the trend analysis of the class variable fluoride and TDS, pH respectively. The standard value of the fluoride, TDS should be around 500 ppm, and pH should be less than 1 and in between 6.5 to 8.5 respectively. Figure 8 shows the violin plot of the class, fluoride, and TDS, pH variable respectively.

Figure 8. Plot of trend analysis, class variable and fluoride and TDS and pH

Figure 9. Violin plot, class variable and fluoride and TDS and pH

For clustering, which is also used as comparison algorithm, KNN is used. The overall MSE of 0.032 and accuracy of 0.974645 was achieved and the classification report of the decision tree algorithm is as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Classification report of KNN algorithm

Classification report	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Support
Class 0	0.9	0.27	0.42	33
Class 1	0.98	1	0.99	953
Micro average	0.97	0.97	0.97	986
Macro average	0.94	0.64	0.7	986
Weighted average	0.97	0.97	0.97	986

4. CONCLUSION

In summary, using the historical data of the water quality of 5000 samples of 14 WQI parameters are trained and tested using different soft computing techniques like: decision tree algorithm with SVM, KNN classifier, linear discriminant analysis, Naïve Bayes classifier and logistic regression. All the algorithms are trained, and the accuracy of the algorithm is calculated. Out of all these decision tree algorithms had the highest accuracy and hence the study is further carried out with decision tree algorithms. The prediction accuracy (0.99) of this algorithm and MSE (0.05) is calculated which is found to be far better than other algorithms. Trend analysis of few important water parameters like pH, Fluoride and TDS is plotted which shows the variations of the values as time increases. KNN algorithm used as a clustering algorithm to plot the classes (good and bad). Also, the accuracy (0.97), and MSE (0.32) show its performance is poorer when compared to decision tree algorithm.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by National Rural Drinking Water Programme (NRDWP) Udupi District Karnataka providing original WQI dataset and environmental laboratory, Department of Civil Engineering, Manipal Institute of Technology, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, and Manipal for helping to understand the laboratory approach to test the quality of drinking water.

FUNDING INFORMATION

Authors state there is no funding involved.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Krishnamurthy Nayak	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓				✓
Sumukha K Nayak		✓				✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
Supreetha Balavalikar Shivaram	✓		✓	✓			✓			✓	✓		✓	✓

C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state that there is no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, [Balavalikar Shivaram Supreetha], upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Khurana and R. Sen, "Drinking water quality in rural India: Issues and approaches," *Drinking water quality, WaterAid. Zambia*, 2008.
- [2] C. Ingrao, R. Strippoli, G. Lagioia, and D. Huisingh, "Water scarcity in agriculture: An Overview of Causes, Impacts and approaches for reducing the risk, *Heliyon*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1-16, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon. 2023.e18507.
- [3] A. K. Batabyal and S. Chakraborty, "Hydro geochemistry, and water quality index in the assessment of groundwater quality for drinking uses," *Water Environment Research*, vol. 87, no. 7, pp. 607-617, 2015, doi: 10.2175/106143015X14212658613956
- [4] Z. Abdulkadir, A. Ibrahim, A. Muhammad, S. A. Sani, and M. A. Baballe, "The water monitoring system disadvantages," *Global Journal of Research in Engineering & Computer Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 5-10, 2023, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8161049.
- [5] M. Najafzadeh and A. Ghaemi, "Prediction of the five-day biochemical oxygen demand and chemical oxygen demand in natural streams using machine learning methods," *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, vol. 191, no. 380, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s10661-019-7446-8.
- [6] M. S. Hanoon *et al.*, "Application of Soft computing in predicting Groundwater quality parameters," *Frontiers in Environmental Sciences*, vol. 10, pp.1-16, doi:10.3389/fenvs.2022.828251.
- [7] N. Vijayakumar and R. Ramya, "The real time monitoring of water quality in IoT environment," *2015 International Conference on Circuits, Power and Computing Technologies [ICCPCT-2015]*, Nagercoil, India, 2015, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICCPCT.2015.7159459.
- [8] A. Omambia, B. Maake, and A. Wambua, "Water quality monitoring using IoT & machine learning," *2022 IST-Africa Conference (IST-Africa)*, Ireland, 2022, pp. 1-8, doi: 10.23919/IST-Africa56635.2022.9845590.
- [9] P. Vasistha and R. Ganguly, "Water quality assessment of natural lakes and its importance: An overview," *Materailstoday: Proceedings*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 544-552, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.02.092.
- [10] R. Altenburger *et al.*, "Future water quality monitoring: improving the balance between exposure and toxicity assessments of real-world pollutant mixtures," *Environmental Sciences Europe*, vol. 31, no. 12, pp. 1-17, 2019, doi: 10.1186/s12302-019-0193-1.
- [11] M. R. Aneesh, "Quality of drinking water and sanitation in India," *Indian Journal of Human Development*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 138-150, 2021, doi: 10.1177/0973703021100365.
- [12] B. S. Maddodi, Prajas, and H. N. U. Shankara, "Evaluation of anthropogenic activities in Udyavara River Basin, Southwest Coast of India," *IJRET: International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*, vol. 4, no. 8, pp. 45-51, 2015.
- [13] K. R. S. R. Raju and G. H. K. Varma, "Knowledge based real time monitoring system for aquaculture using IoT," *2017 IEEE 7th International Advance Computing Conference (IACC)*, Hyderabad, India, 2017, pp. 318-321, doi: 10.1109/IACC.2017.0075.
- [14] Central Pollution Control Board, *Report of the Performance Audit of State Pollution Control Boards / Pollution Control Committees*, Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, New Delhi, India, pp. 161-168, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://cpcb.nic.in>
- [15] Karnataka State Pollution Control Board, *Annual Report 2019-20*, Bangalore, India, pp. 119-130, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://kspcb.karnataka.gov.in>
- [16] W. Chungyalpa, "Examination and analysis of the Central Pollution Control Board and the State Pollution Control Board-Indian Administrative Arm for Environmental protection," *Indian Journal of Sustainable Development*, vol.6, no. 1, pp. 11-21, 2021.

- [17] P. Ravikumar, M. A. Mehmood, and R. K. Somashekar, "Water quality index to determine the surface water quality of Sankey Tank and Mallathahalli Lake, Bangalore Urban District, Karnataka, India," *Applied Water Science*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 247-261, 2013, doi: 10.1007/s13201-013-0077-2.
- [18] N. T. Giao, H. T. H. Nhien, P. K. Anh, and P. Thuptimdang, "Groundwater quality assessment for drinking purposes: a case study in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam," *Scientific reports*, vol. 13, no. 4380, pp. 1-13, 2023, doi: 10.1038/s41598-023-31621-9.
- [19] Y. Madrid and Z. P. Zayas, "Water sampling: traditional methods and new approaches in water sampling strategy," *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 293-299, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.trac.2007.01.002.
- [20] U. Ahmed, R. Mumtaz, H. Anwar, S. Mumtaz, and A. M. Qamar, "Water quality monitoring: From conventional to emerging technologies," *Corrigendum: Water Supply*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 28-25, 2020, doi: 10.2166/ws.2019.144.
- [21] C. R. Ramakrishnaiah, C. Sadashivaiah, and G. Ranganna, "Assessment of water quality index for the groundwater in Tumkur Taluk," *Journal of Chemistry, India*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 523-530, 2009, doi: 10.1155/2009/757424.
- [22] S. N. Zainurin *et al.*, "Advancements in monitoring water quality based on various sensing methods: A systematic review," *International Journal of Environmental Health and Public Health*, vol. 19, no. 21, pp. 1-21, 2022, doi: 10.3390/ijerph192114080.
- [23] K. Nayak, S. B. S. D. M., and V. Nayak, "E-Nose system to detect E-Coli in drinking water of Udupi District," *International Journal of Engineering Research and Development*, vol. 1, no. 12, pp. 58-64, 2012.
- [24] B. P. Radhakrishna and R. Vaidyanadhan, "Geology of Karnataka," *Geological Society of India*, Bangalore, 1994.
- [25] S. Raghavan, J. Jayaram, A. Lakshmisha, P. Agarwal, M. Nikham, and B. Nagendra, *Report on Current Water Resources, Water Governance Institutional Arrangements, Water Related Policies, Cross-boundary Issues & Agreements of Karnataka State*, Advanced Center for Integrated Water Resource Management, Karnataka, India, pp. 1-4, 2017.
- [26] Central Ground Water Board, "National compilation in dynamic groundwater resources of India-2017," *Ministry of Jal Shakti, Department of Water Resources, River Development & Ganga Rejuvenation*, Government of India, Faridabad, Jul. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://ruralindiaonline.org/hi/library/resource/national-compilation-on-dynamic-ground-water-resources-of-india-2017/>

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Krishnamurthy Nayak received the B.Tech. degree in Electronics and Communication Engineering from Manipal Institute of Technology, Manipal and the Master's degree in Industrial Biotechnology and the Ph.D. degree in Electronics Engineering from Dr. M.G.R Educational and Research Institute, Chennai, India. He is currently a Professor at Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, MAHE, Manipal. His current research interests include soft computing, application for environmental susceptibility, design of bio and micro sensors for environmental applications and MEMS Technology. He worked on Philips funded project for developing electronic smart shoe for his credit. He can be contacted at email: km.nayak@manipal.edu.

Sumukha K. Nayak third-year undergraduate student at BITS Pilani with a keen interest in the intersection of mathematics, technology, and finance. With a strong foundation in optimization, linear algebra, and statistical methods, he is passionate about applying mathematical principles to real-world problems, particularly in the domains of deep learning and quantitative finance. His experience in competitive sports such as state-level chess and table tennis has honed his focus, strategic mindset, and discipline traits that reflect in his technical pursuits. He can be contacted at email: f20230932@pilani.bits-pilani.ac.in.

Supreetha Balavalikar Shivaram received B.Tech. degree in Electronics and Communication engineering from Mangalore University and the Master's degree in Microelectronics and the Ph.D. degree in Electronics Engineering from Manipal Institute of Technology, Manipal, India She is currently a Professor at Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, MAHE, Manipal. Her current research interests include soft computing, application for environmental susceptibility, design of bio and micro sensors for environmental applications and MEMS Technology, analog system design. She can be contacted at email: supreetha.bs@manipal.edu.